

Reproducing Cross-Lingual Document Retrieval Using Regularized Wasserstein Distance

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CCS Concepts: • Information systems → Similarity measures; Probabilistic retrieval models.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: Wasserstein Distance, Reproduction

1 INTRODUCTION

In this report we are examining the experiment conducted in the paper [1] "Cross-Lingual Document Retrieval Using Regularized Wasserstein Distance" by Georgios Balikas, Charlotte Laclau, Ievgen Redko and Massih-Reza Amini and try reproducing their results. The paper approaches the problem of cross-lingual document retrieval (CLDR), specifically concerned with finding the same article in a different language, by making use of the Wasserstein metric to measure the distance of two documents. With the bag-of-words model (BOW) one can model documents (and its words) as high-dimensional probability densities. The Wasserstein distance (also: World Mover's Distance) is derived from optimal transport (OT) theory and finds a map that "minimizes the total transportation cost given a ground metric for transferring the first density to the second. The ground metric for text data can be estimated using word embeddings" [5] as cited by [1]. As we have a cross-lingual setting here, we have a common space for both embeddings, as this allows calculating distance metrics between words of different languages.

The major contribution of the paper is not the use of the metric for text data, but by extending it in multiple ways. Firstly, they modify the weighting scheme to not only support straight term frequencies in the document vector, but also incorporating the inverse-document frequency (IDF) by multiplying IDF with the term frequency. In addition, normalization is performed. To make things more clear, we refer to this setting – in contrast to the paper – as TF-IDF instead of just IDF. Another contribution is the application of entropic regularization of optimal transport [2]. This speeds up the computation and leads to smoother and more stable results, as it allows applying the Sinkhorn-Knopp matrix algorithm [1, 2]. Lastly, a major extension is the handling of the out-of-vocabulary words (OOV). Not every word in a document has a corresponding word embedding. This missing data problem has significant effects, as the preprocessed document incorporates only words and their embeddings, which simply drops all out-of-vocabulary words. To overcome this, they measure the Levenshtein distance of each OOV to every word in the embeddings dictionary. If this distance is below a threshold (in this case 1 - inclusive) it is added to the processed document vector. Therefore, words, with a maximum of 1 edit operations apart, are matched. If there are multiple words, one is drawn at random. Another aspect of the OOV protocol is that the same words and their cross-lingual embeddings are collapsed. If, e.g., the word "transition" occurs both in a French and an English document the embedding of the language with higher dictionary size is used in every case [1]. Therefore, a processed French document may incorporate an English word embedding, which brings those two documents closer in the shared embedding space.

Strictly speaking, with our work we wanted to replicate the results of the paper and not vary its setup, as by far not all of the code was given. Following Plesser [6] replication tries to re-create the results with the same experimental setup by a different team. Reproduction, in the narrow sense, tries to re-create results with a different experimental setup and

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a different team, therefore, completely re-implementing artefacts from scratch. We interpreted the task description to target replicability in our case, however, due to missing code, we extended and modified the given experimental setup slightly so that it is no strict replicability anymore.

2 EXPERIMENT

The experiment is performed by using a cross-lingual dataset¹ from linguatoools.org, which incorporates matching documents from Wikipedia. Four language pairs are compared: English-French, English-German, English-Finnish and English-Greek. Each experiment is performed in both ways, e.g. French-English and English-French. The use of various languages brings interesting insights, as different alphabets (e.g. the Greek alphabet) or language-specific symbols, such as umlauts, are used. To reduce the computational complexity, the amount of document pairs to compare for each language is restricted to 500. Additionally, only the first 500 words per document are extracted. Documents smaller than 5 words (with a corresponding embedding) are omitted.

For comparing the results other state of the art approaches are applied to the same dataset. As depicted in the first three sections of table 1 there are three general paradigms of CLDR compared. Firstly, a topic modelling approach using bilingual Latent Dirichlet Allocation (BiLDA), which maps cross-lingual topics in a shared space to perform comparisons. Secondly, translation based systems where the queried document is translated to the target language and subsequently compared by using popular methods, such as the euclidean distance of the TF or TF-IDF vectors. Thirdly, the family of systems that rely on cross-lingual word embeddings, which is the main focus of this paper. Besides the Wasserstein distance (in regularized or unregularized form) the neural bag of words model (nBow) is used in this context with, again, the variation of the TF versus TF-IDF representation of the documents. The nBow method averages every dimension of all the word embeddings in a document and weights it using a neural network [7]. Subsequently, similarity is measured by using the euclidean distance. Note that each method in the family of cross-lingual embeddings can also be used for translation based systems, which the authors of the paper did as well. In addition to the three general paradigms, the aforementioned extension of the cross-lingual embeddings – the OOV handling – was implemented as well (4th section of the table). In this setting, the same methods as previously were applied in combination with a different preprocessing procedure, namely the OOV handling.

By applying all those methods we get a ranking of possibly relevant documents according to the chosen distance metric. There is exactly one match ("Known-search problem" [1]). Therefore, the mean reciprocal rank (MRR) was chosen as the target performance measure to optimize. No statistical hypothesis testing was done by the authors nor were any confidence intervals or p-values given.

3 REPLICATION

To replicate the results of the paper, we used the code in the GitHub repo² uploaded by the authors. The script provides the code for the unregularized and regularized version of the Wasserstein distance and also supports TF and TF-IDF weighting schemes. When running the code, the script downloads the embeddings. The language data for French and English can already be found in the repository. Also, the importing and the basic preprocessing of those embeddings and documents are applied. (More or less) out of the box, we could reproduce 8 (2 languages x 2 weighting schemes [TF vs TF-IDF] x 2 versions [regularization vs. no regularization]) of the 168 results of table 1. Those are highlighted green.

¹<https://linguatoools.org/tools/corpora/wikipedia-comparable-corpora/> (Accessed at 20th of January 2022)

²<https://github.com/balikasg/WassersteinRetrieval> (Accessed at 20th of January 2022)

	En → Fr	Fr → En	En → Ge	Ge → En	En → Gr	Gr → En	En → Fi	Fi → En
Systems that rely on topic models								
BiLDA	.559	.468	.560	.536	.559	.508	.622	.436
Systems that rely on translations								
tf	.421	.278	.287	.433	.441	.054	.068	.025
idf	.575	.433	.478	.516	.535	.126	.081	.028
nBOW _{tf}	.404	.276	.378	.440	.531	.132	.329	.042
nBOW _{idf}	.550	.488	.449	.509	.577	.256	.398	.081
Wass _{tf}	.704	.691	.620	.655	.656	.269	.424	.092
Wass _{idf} *	.748	.766	.678	.706	.687	.463	.412	.163
Entro_Wass _{tf} *	.692	.706	.615	.666	.640	.262	.422	.089
Entro_Wass _{idf} *	.745	.794	.675	.720	.683	.467	.425	.171
Systems that rely on cross-lingual embeddings								
nBOW _{tf}	.530	.490	.493	.464	.237	.121	.449	.217
nBOW _{idf}	.574	.546	.521	.502	.341	.179	.470	.267
Wass _{tf}	.744	.748	.660	.681	.404	.407	.582	.434
Wass _{idf} *	.778	.784	.703	.718	.507	.465	.620	.479
Entro_Wass _{tf} *	.753	.786	.677	.710	.424	.494	.582	.607
Entro_Wass _{idf} *	.799	.820	.717	.756	.523	.549	.620	.643
Handling OOV words & cross-lingual embeddings								
nBOW _{tf+}	.518	.541	.426	.468	.193	.148	.635	.451
nBOW _{idf+}	.653	.659	.597	.592	.407	.349	.693	.544
Wass _{tf+}	.815	.836	.788	.801	.675	.435	.845	.731
Wass _{idf+} *	.867	.869	.812	.837	.721	.599	.856	.786
Entro_Wass _{tf+} *	.830	.856	.796	.812	.718	.555	.851	.816
Entro_Wass _{idf+} *	.875	.887	.828	.855	.741	.695	.864	.850

Table 1. Results from the paper [1]. Out-of-the-box replication is highlighted green. Custom replication by adding data is highlighted blue and the results that could be replicated with the custom implementation of OOV handling is highlighted yellow.

On a machine with 32GB of RAM, 4GHz quad core Intel i7 6700k) this took approximately 5 hours per language pair. Doing that we were able to replicate the exact numbers of the paper.

To replicate the experiment for the six missing languages pairs we manually downloaded the Wikipedia comparable corpora from linguatools. Not only was the source-file’s structure different, but also the code generating the language files was missing and the XML source-file generally corrupted. Therefore, we re-engineered this step (see section 4). This increased the amount of replicable results from 8 to 32. In table 1 this is highlighted in blue. Although, we took the same dataset of the same year, the extraction method returned slightly different result language files. This led to the issue that we did not have the exact same input data anymore when comparing the data to the articles that was already included in the repository. Therefore, we could also not replicate the exact same numbers.

The OOV handling is a major aspect of the method and improved the results significantly. However, it was completely missing from the published code. We therefore dug into the paper to fully understand this OOV protocol and re-engineered it ourselves. This doubled the amount of results from 32 to 64 of 168, highlighted yellow in table 1. Therefore, we could re-run the method proposed in the paper in all its variations.

157 However, all the algorithms generating the comparative results, including topic-modeling based, translation based
158 and nBOW (for cross-lingual embeddings) were not provided in the code as well. Due to lack of information about the
159 implementation and details of these algorithms in the paper, the other results could not be reproduced in a reasonable
160 amount of time and without a high amount of uncertainty.
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162 With respect to the PRIMAD model [4] we basically prime the input data, the implementation and the involved
163 actors of the experiment. By changing the input data we can make statements about the generalization capabilities of
164 the algorithm. By re-implementing the OOV handling and by extending the languages we can evaluate the "correctness
165 of the implementation" and its efficiency [4].
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168 4 DIFFICULTIES

169 This sections describes the issues we were confronted with in more detail.
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172 4.1 Running the code

173 We followed the instructions provided in the repository and realized that there is missing information in order to re-run
174 the experiment. Firstly, no environment definition has been made. For Python, this could have either been done via a
175 *requirements.txt*, *setup.py* or an anaconda's *environment.yml* file. As simply installing the newest version of the used
176 packages did not work, we had to do some trial-and-error in order to find the right versions for all the libraries. On top
177 of that, the use of the outdated Python version 2.7 did not ease this task. In addition to the missing packages, the NLTK³
178 library required some resources that had as well been downloaded manually. We improved the code by including an
179 environment definition and an NLTK initialization function, which downloads its dependencies. After resolving those
180 conflicts, we were able to run the script.
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185 4.2 Missing data

186 The experiment uses data for the document-language-pairs and the embeddings. To support the language comparisons
187 of the paper, we had to extend both. The easier task was to acquire the embeddings, which are extracted from a giant
188 numberbatch⁴ text file with a provided script. The extension of the script for other languages was straight-forward.
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190 In contrast, the acquisition of the Wikipedia language files was cumbersome. The preprocessing code that generates
191 the line-separated document collections from the linguatool comparable corpora XML source-file was missing. What
192 first seemed to be easy to fix was harder then expected. For each Wikipedia document, the HTML body was inserted
193 into the XML, which made the XML file invalid due to the relaxed restrictions of HTML, such as the non-necessity of
194 closing tags. Therefore, extracting information by using XPath or similar tools was completely infeasible. After some
195 trial and error we changed the strategy and found a small repository on GitHub⁵ that a generous user submitted. By
196 using some of the code provided we were able to parse the XML with regular expressions instead of XML-parsers.
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199 What is more, no timestamps for the Wikipedia language files were given. For a dynamic data source such as
200 Wikipedia this clearly resulted in different files, a slightly different experimental setting and therefore to different
201 results. On the other hand, this allows evaluating the robustness of the method.
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205 ³<https://www.nltk.org> (Accessed at 21st of January 2022)

206 ⁴<https://github.com/commonsense/conceptnet-numberbatch> (Accessed at 21st of January 2022)

207 ⁵<https://github.com/ponshane/Wiki-Bilingual-Co-Occurence-Matrix> (Accessed at 21st of January 2022)

4.3 OOV handling

For implementing the out-of-vocabulary handling described in the paper we adapted the document preprocessing. For every word not in the word embedding dictionary we compute the Levenshtein distance to all other embeddings. This computation is only performed, if the OOV word is neither a stop word nor a punctuation symbol or a number, as described in the paper. However, we had major issues regarding performance due to the computational complexity of the Levenshtein distance with $O(n \cdot (w_1 \cdot w_2))$ for word #1 with length w_1 and word #2 with length w_2 and n for the number of word embeddings. We therefore implemented some adaptations to reduce the runtime:

- Caching the candidate embeddings for each word. If words occur multiple times, the lookup is faster as the costly computation is not required.
- Applying parallelization by multiprocessing the computation in order to make use of multiple cores.
- Vectorizing the operations using numpy.

After those improvements the runtime was reduced to 8h hours per language pair and the OOV data could be computed within 4 days. The implementation took us some time as we had no experience in Python performance computing yet and also due to troubles with some missing features of Python 2.7 (e.g. no Jupyter-Notebook support or the less usable multiprocessing implementation).

4.4 Comparison results

As mentioned above, we were not able to reproduce all the comparison metrics. The following explains why.

4.4.1 Topic modelling based systems. The authors trained a BiLDA model for each language pair. Although hyperparameters were given in the paper it was infeasible for us to recreate it without any hints on how to implement this algorithm or any description of the underlying model.

4.4.2 Systems that rely on translations. By translating the query document to the target language usual distance metrics, like euclidean distance, can be used. However, for this method to work, the translation model is of utmost importance. The authors used a dictionary-based approach by generating dictionaries for each language-pair using Wiktionary. As there are multiple translation candidates for each word, they picked a "candidate translation according to a unigram language model learned on 'BiLDA training' data" [1]. No hyperparameters nor any implementation hints were given, making a replication infeasible. As valid comparisons would therefore be questionable, we did not implement the whole family of translation based systems.

4.4.3 Neural bag-of-words (nBOW). A quite similar approach to the Wasserstein distance is nBOW, which also uses cross-lingual embeddings. Aside from the averaging of the word embeddings (which is rather straight-forward), the neuronal network with a fully-connected layer (that computes the weights of the resulting vectors) was unfeasible to obtain. Again there was no code or information provided on how to train the model.

5 RESULTS

Initially we planned to fully replicate the experiment in its original form to get the exact numbers of the paper. However, as we had to re-code and re-collect/extract the data, we obviously slightly re-arranged the experiment. The main reason for the different results of table 2 is because the data is slightly different. However, we still have very good results that support the main claims stated in the paper. Firstly, the TF-IDF representation tends to perform better than the TF.

	En → Fr	Fr → En	En → Ge	Ge → En	En → Gr	Gr → En	En → Fi	Fi → En
Systems that rely on cross-lingual embeddings								
<i>nBow_{tf}</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>nBow_{tf-idf}</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Wass_{tf}</i>	0.792	0.858	0.604	0.628	0.448	0.37	0.55	0.394
<i>Wass_{tf-idf}</i>	0.884	0.886	0.64	0.646	0.472	0.372	0.6	0.432
<i>Entro_{Wass_{tf}}</i>	0.818	0.906	0.61	0.646	0.436	0.456	0.56	0.558
<i>Entro_{Wass_{tf-idf}}</i>	0.882	0.924	0.658	0.7	0.45	0.504	0.598	0.606
Handling OOV Words & cross-lingual embeddings								
<i>nBow_{tf}</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>nBow_{tf-idf}</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Wass_{tf}</i>	0.848	0.92	0.66	0.638	0.608	0.51	0.734	0.516
<i>Wass_{tf-idf}</i>	0.886	0.928	0.704	0.69	0.618	0.528	0.744	0.548
<i>Entro_{Wass_{tf}}</i>	0.84	0.958	0.668	0.676	0.612	0.644	0.736	0.674
<i>Entro_{Wass_{tf-idf}}</i>	0.878	0.958	0.71	0.716	0.622	0.672	0.748	0.71

Table 2. Replication of results

Also, the regularized version of the algorithm tends to perform better than the unregularized one. The re-coded OOV handling strategy improve the results in nearly all the cases significantly. This especially applies to the regularized language pairs with different alphabets, like English-Finnish and English-Greek, improving the MRR by up to 0.2. Generally, the ranking of the performance of the language pairs matches the paper, although the numbers are not exactly the same, the patterns are. Unfortunately, the comparison to other methods could not be reproduced.

6 REMARKS AND CONCLUSIONS

There are some aspects about the experiments that raised some questions. Firstly, for each document, words without embeddings, stop words, punctuation symbols and numbers are omitted. For the latter we wonder why this has been done, as e.g. Wikipedia articles with common numbers (like birth dates) may tend to be more similar. The authors did not discuss this particular decision and it is therefore speculation. Secondly, what we missed a bit in the paper was the bad runtime performance, which was only mentioned in the context of training and prediction, but not regarding the OOV protocol. However, in our case, this strategy was the clear performance bottleneck of the experiment, which took us 4 days to run 24/7. Thirdly, in the published code we saw that the document pairs are not selected randomly, but just by cutting of necessary samples by still preserving the order from the linguatools dataset. This may introduce some bias. As we do not have the data-extraction code, we cannot conclude if this has been done beforehand. Due to the long runtime of the experiments we did not try changing those parameters and investigate their consequences. What also has not been done is any cross-validation or statistical significance testing. Therefore, the experimental design may be prone to some influence of the selection method of the training data.

7 REMAINING WORK

To fully replicate the paper one would need to look into the comparative models as well in order to proof whether the presented method really outperforms the others or not. However, as we were able to reproduce the major parts of the paper, we are sure that the authors worked according to scientific standards. In this exercise we did something in-between of reproducing and replicating the experiment. Following Drummond [3] pure replication "is the weakest of

all possible reproductions of an experimental result" and basically just fraud detection. Therefore, it would make more sense to apply the proposed method in completely different experimental setup and examine its performance with a complete different dataset.

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